

Implication of Birch and Swinnerton-Dyer Conjecture with β Function

Jihyeon Yoon*

(Doctor of Korean Medicine, Shinhwa Geriatric Hospital)

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Abstract

β function in continued fractions forms reality of Fermion-Dirac and Bose-Einstein statistics everytime stochastic distribution event happens. And entropy is decided everytime uniquely.

1 Introduction

There is interesting property in β function related with Birch and Swinnerton-Dyer Conjecture. And the property sets causalities to Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein statistics property, so that countable event in ensemble entropy change structures into one single number.

2 β functionality in Ensemble Statistics

$$P(E_{state}) = \begin{cases} \text{Fermi-Dirac} \Rightarrow \frac{1}{\exp \frac{-(E_{state} - \mu_{state})}{kT} + 1} \\ \text{Bose-Einstein} \Rightarrow \frac{1}{\exp \frac{-(E_{state} - \mu_{state})}{kT} - 1} \end{cases} \Rightarrow \sum_{states} P(E_{state}) = 1$$

What we see here is that any energy expression is another form of countable event, which can be a number of ensemble that set of particles that can take. So, every event form of situation can be translated in one kind of temperature, and one temperature must be in rational number that can be fractioned into another fraction.

Then what this can mean in β function?

$$B(m, n) = \frac{(m-1)!(n-1)!}{(m+n-1)!}, \frac{1}{\pi B(x, 1-x)} = \sin \pi x$$

3 Two Kind of Trigonometry: Sine and Cosine

$$\frac{1}{\pi B(x, 1-x)} = \sin \pi x \Rightarrow \cos \pi x = \frac{1}{\pi B(x+1/2, 1/2-x)}$$

Furthermore, we can use our trigonometric imagination.

$$\sin^2 \pi x + \cos^2 \pi x = \left(\frac{1}{\pi B(x, 1-x)} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{1}{\pi B(x+1/2, 1/2-x)} \right)^2 = 1$$

*Jihyeon Yoon is a korean medicine doctor. And he is a freelancer programmer also.

E-mail: flyingtext@nate.com, somehowme@gmail.com

Yeongdeungpo-gu, Seoul, 07429,

Seoul, South Korea

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9610-0994>

And what we see here is a butterfly.

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left(\frac{1}{B(x, 1-x)} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{1}{B(x+1/2, 1/2-x)} \right)^2 = \pi^2 \\
\Rightarrow \pi^2 \sin^2 \pi x &= \left(\frac{1}{B(x, 1-x)} \right)^2 = \left(\pi - \frac{1}{B(x+1/2, 1/2-x)} \right) \left(\pi + \frac{1}{B(x+1/2, 1/2-x)} \right) \\
&= \left(\pi - \frac{1}{B \left(x + \frac{\pi \sin^2 \pi x + \pi \cos^2 \pi x}{2\pi}, \frac{\pi \sin^2 \pi x + \pi \cos^2 \pi x}{2\pi} - x \right)} \right) \\
&\cdot \left(\pi + \frac{1}{B \left(x + \frac{\pi \sin^2 \pi x + \pi \cos^2 \pi x}{2\pi}, \frac{\pi \sin^2 \pi x + \pi \cos^2 \pi x}{2\pi} - x \right)} \right) \\
&= \left(\pi - \frac{1}{B \left(x + \frac{\pi \left(\frac{1}{\pi B(x, 1-x)} \right)^2 + \pi \left(\frac{1}{\pi B(x+1/2, 1/2-x)} \right)^2}{2\pi}, \frac{\pi \left(\frac{1}{\pi B(x, 1-x)} \right)^2 + \pi \left(\frac{1}{\pi B(x+1/2, 1/2-x)} \right)^2}{2\pi} - x \right)} \right) \\
&\cdot \left(\pi + \frac{1}{B \left(x + \frac{\pi \left(\frac{1}{\pi B(x, 1-x)} \right)^2 + \pi \left(\frac{1}{\pi B(x+1/2, 1/2-x)} \right)^2}{2\pi}, \frac{\pi \left(\frac{1}{\pi B(x, 1-x)} \right)^2 + \pi \left(\frac{1}{\pi B(x+1/2, 1/2-x)} \right)^2}{2\pi} - x \right)} \right) \\
&= \dots \\
\Rightarrow \pi^2 \cos^2 \pi x &= \left(\frac{1}{B(x+1/2, 1/2-x)} \right)^2 = \left(\pi - \frac{1}{B(x, 1-x)} \right) \left(\pi + \frac{1}{B(x, 1-x)} \right) \\
&= \left(\pi - \frac{1}{B \left(x, \left(\frac{1}{\pi B(x, 1-x)} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{1}{\pi B(x+1/2, 1/2-x)} \right)^2 - x \right)} \right) \left(\pi + \frac{1}{B \left(x, \left(\frac{1}{\pi B(x, 1-x)} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{1}{\pi B(x+1/2, 1/2-x)} \right)^2 - x \right)} \right) \\
&= \dots
\end{aligned}$$

What can be seen here is that parameters in β function forms symmetry from 1 to 1/2 and furthermore expanding conserving its parametric structure.

4 Stochastic Process in Continued Fractal(or Fraction)

So the reason why to face continued fraction reveals at stochastic process. Any angle consist another β driven another angle in continued fraction. And then the fractal is conquered. And remebering the foregonis is conserved by the angle every β function engages. So another unique number in formulation in counting number of cases can be given. So the fractal control achieved while conserving the sum total of two statistics.

So with Euler's continued fraction[Cretney(2014)]:

$$a_0 + a_0 a_1 + \dots + a_0 a_1 a_2 \dots a_n = \frac{a_0}{1 - \frac{a_1}{1 + a_1 - \frac{a_2}{1 + a_2 - \frac{\ddots}{\ddots - \frac{a_{n-1}}{1 + a_{n-1} - \frac{a_n}{1 + a_n}}}}}$$

5 Countability Provided within L-function

For cases:

$$a_0 = a_0$$

$$a_0 + a_0a_1 = \frac{a_0}{1 - \frac{a_1}{1 + a_1}}$$

$$a_0 + a_0a_1 + a_0a_1a_2 = \frac{a_0}{1 - \frac{a_1}{1 + a_1 - \frac{a_2}{1 + a_2}}}$$

What we see here is that any countability provided by integer sequence a and its formation in Euler's continued fraction with its partial form, can be assured its uniqueness with L-function. With the collorary provided in Birch and Swinnerton-Dyer conjecture[Yoon(2024)], this formation is guaranteed with prime numbers within countable finitude repeats. This is important in sense that any parameter that is given to β function cannot be countable or have finitude structure in continued repeats, the number that β function provides cannot be formed as rational number in continued fraction repeat again.

For instance, from repeats that are not finitude, the equation cannot be determined in rational set:

$$(a_0 + a_0a_1 + a_0a_1a_2 + a_0a_1a_2a_3) = \frac{a_0}{1 - \frac{a_1}{1 + a_1 - \frac{a_2}{1 + a_2 - \dots}}}$$

$$\Rightarrow \text{Let } X_1 = 1 + a_1 - \frac{a_2}{1 + a_2 - \dots}$$

$$(a_0 + a_0a_1 + a_0a_1a_2 + a_0a_1a_2a_3 + a_0a_1a_2a_3a_4) = \frac{a_0}{1 - \frac{a_1}{1 + a_1 - \frac{a_2}{1 + a_2 - \frac{a_3}{1 + a_3 - \dots}}}}$$

$$\Rightarrow \text{Let } X_2 = 1 + a_2 - \frac{a_3}{1 + a_3 - \dots} \implies X_1 = 1 + a_1 - \frac{a_2}{X_2} \quad (s.t. a, X \in \mathbf{Q})$$

For showing contrary that finite series in a, X provides rational result in continued fraction, assuming that the sequence a, X is infinite series, there is counterexample case of $\ln x$ being in form of infinitely continued fraction.

$$\log(1+x) = \frac{x}{1 - \frac{\frac{-x}{2}}{1 + \frac{-x}{2} - \frac{\frac{-2x}{3}}{1 + \frac{-2x}{3} - \frac{\frac{-3x}{4}}{1 + \frac{-3x}{4} - \dots}}}}$$

So the every physical event is finitely countable in their sense that they exist. And by the guarantee from their existence unique in their determination, every entropy differentiates from another existing one within rational range.

6 Expanding Rational to Complex Plane

To demonstrate ensemble statistics driven by the adequate continued fraction relatable with β function, the importance of Euler's equation can be revisited.

$$e^{\pi i} = -1$$

From upper equation, relations between the constants can be driven:

$$e^{e^{\pi i}} = \frac{1}{e}$$

$$\Rightarrow e^{e^{\pi i} \cdot \pi i} = -1$$

Assuming that $g = e^{\pi i}$, $g^g = -1$. This g^g formed -1 has good properties as following:

1. $g = g^g = g^{g^g} = -1$
2. $g^{\frac{1}{2}} = g^{\frac{1}{2}g} = i$
3. $g^\theta = g^{g^\theta} = \cos \theta + i \sin \theta = -g \cos \theta + g^{\frac{1}{2}} \sin \theta$
4. $g^{-\theta} = g^{-g^\theta} = \cos \theta - i \sin \theta = -g \cos \theta - g^{\frac{1}{2}} \sin \theta$

So the half integer powered to g^g creates unit of imaginary number i , while the integer powered to g^g creates unit of integer number -1 .

$$\cos \theta = -(g^\theta + g^{-\theta})/2g = (g^\theta + g^{-\theta})/2$$

$$\sin \theta = -(g^\theta - g^{-\theta})/2g = (g^\theta - g^{-\theta})/2$$

And again, we can format equation in continued fraction again.

$$4 = 4(\sin^2 \theta + \cos^2 \theta) = (g^\theta + g^{-\theta})^2 + (g^\theta - g^{-\theta})^2 = 2g^{2\theta} + 2g^{-2\theta} = 2(g^\theta + ig^{-\theta})(g^\theta - ig^{-\theta})$$

$$= 2(g^\theta - i(\cos \theta - i \sin \theta))(g^\theta + i(\cos \theta + i \sin \theta))$$

This provides hint toward Yukawa term (regarding electromagnetic field) in Standard Model with tensor product to have $-1/4$ divided in Lagrangian when universal sum total counts in. With hyperbolic space provided in $\sin \theta$ and $\cos \theta$ to be in their min and max values in area of $\sin^2 \theta + \cos^2 \theta$ requires rank at least 4 to keep universality of tensor. So to sum up maximum vectors to fit interaction with other term, $-1/4$ multiplication appears – which eventually conserves $e^{\pi i}$.

7 Conclusion: Bridge between Ensemble Statistics and Continued Fraction

So to sum up, the event cases that constitute ensemble statistics takes symmetric continued fraction form. Then, with every given case of unique θ in which can be presented in form of $e^{\theta i}$:

$$P(\theta_{state}) = \begin{cases} \text{Fermi-Dirac} \Rightarrow \frac{1}{\exp \frac{-(\Sigma\theta - \theta_{state})}{kT} + 1} \\ \text{Bose-Einstein} \Rightarrow \frac{1}{\exp \frac{-(\Sigma\theta - \theta_{state})}{kT} - 1} \end{cases} \Rightarrow \sum_{states} P(\theta_{state}) = 1$$

Every state distributed can be expressed in β function in energy. And for so, entropy can has its own discrete (not continuous) form in mass number. Because every entropy is countably one-to-one unique in process of determination with Fermi-Dirac statistics. And for this, β function actuates another number in case.

In suggestion, this “discreteness” provided by unique number of entropy can form undecidability in each spectral gap[Cubitt et al.(2015)Cubitt, Perez-Garcia, and Wolf], leaving every measurement in their own unique situation.

References

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